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SMART HOME

Aneena Joy, Disha Davis, Reshma K R, Steji Rose V J, Nicy K S

Department of Computer Science and Engineering,
IES College of Engineering, Chittilappilly, Thrissur

Abstract:

Objective- Smart Home is an efficient implementation of Internet of Things (IoT) for controlling and monitoring home appliances without much human intervention. This project aims at designing a climbable and price effective home automation system that controls home appliances via smart phone.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- Home automation system uses portable devices as user interface. They can communicate with the home automation network through an Internet gateway, by means of low power communication protocols like Wi-Fi, Zigbee and raspberry pi as server system. Various sensors like PIR sensor, fire detecting sensor, gas leakage detecting sensor and relay drives are used in home automation.

Findings- The user here will move directly with the system through a web-based interface over the web, whereas home appliances like lights, fans are remotely controlled through easy website. An extra feature that enhances the facet of protection is the detection of fire accidents, gas leakage or presence of any intruders.

Limitations- The various future applications may be used by controlling various household devices of house with internet, Industrial automation and management through internet, machine-driven fireplace exit systems, energy and environmental monitoring and improvement of security problems in extremely restricted areas.

Practical implications- The system may be employed in many places like banks, hospitals, labs etc that dramatically cut back the hazard of unauthorized entry. Proof may be given to the safety department if any theft issue happens. It also stores the sensor parameters in the cloud (Gmail) in a timely manner. This will help the user to analyze the condition of various parameters in the home anytime anywhere.

Originality/Value- This paper contains different types of home automation systems based on IoT as literature survey.

Keywords- Raspberry pi, Wi-Fi, Internet of Things, Web Server, Home Automation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, technology has become an integrated part of people's lives. It has, and continues to influence many aspects of daily life and has allowed better social interaction, ease of transportation, the ability to indulge in entertainment and media etc. The creation of many devices such as mobile phones and computers have caused many people to rely on technology to communicate with their friends, store information such as pictures, movies, documents, and music. The internet has become a common interface that many devices use in order to simplify the daily life of many people. Internet helps us to bring in with immediate solution for many problems and also able to connect from any of the remote places which contributes to overall cost reduction and energy consumption.

Internet of things (IoT) can be defined as connecting the various types of objects like Smart Phones, Personal Computer and Tablets to internet, which brings in very newfangled type of communication between things and people and also between things. An advanced network of IoT is being formed when a human being is in need of connecting with other things. IoT technology is used to come in with innovative idea and great growth for smart homes to improve the living standards of life.

The existing home automation systems have made significant contributions to the design and development of home automation systems. However, the existing works were mainly focused on switching and controlling home appliances or connected devices rather than remotely monitoring the home environment. It doesn't provide security against fire accidents, gas leakage and intruders. The data collected from the system is not stored. For example, information such as the time at which the lights were on/off is not stored. The user cannot analyze the condition of various parameters in home.

In our scheme, the main objective is to design and to execute a cost effective and open source home automation system that's capable of leading most of the home and sustain the house automation system. The predictable system contains a great elasticity by using wireless reliable

technology to interconnect various modules to the server of home automation system. This in turn reduces the deployment cost; will add to the flexibility of advancement, and system reconfiguration. The projected system can make use of wireless LAN (Local space Network) connections between various sensors, hardware modules and server, and various communication protocols between users and server.

II. RELATED WORKS

2.1 HOME AUTOMATION USING INTERNET OF THINGS

The main aim of the system is to develop a system that will provide remote control of home appliances and also provides security against the mishaps when the home host is not at home. This paper is mainly concerned with the automatic control of light or any other home appliances using internet. It derives a solution providing better control on home appliances with help of cell phone.

It is meant to save the electric power and human energy. This project is made with the help of controller and raspberry pi. The various appliances connected to the micro controller and sensor is connected using wireless network. This system controls the home appliances like lights and fans, monitors temperature and humidity and detects gas leakage. Advantages of home automation system includes the following.

- Reduced installation costs: First and foremost, installation costs are significantly reduced since no cabling is necessary. Wired solutions require cabling, where material as well as the professional laying of cables (e.g. into walls) is expensive.
- System scalability and easy extension: Deploying a wireless network is especially advantageous when, due to new or changed requirements, extension of the network is necessary. In contrast to wired installations, in which cabling extension is tedious, this makes wireless installations a seminal investment.

2.2 HOME AUTOMATION USING IOT

With advancement of Automation technology, life is getting simpler and easier in all aspects. In today's world Automatic systems are being preferred over manual system. With the

rapid increase in the number of users of internet over the past decade has made Internet a part and parcel of life, and IoT is the latest and emerging internet technology. Internet of things is a growing network of everyday object-from industrial machine to consumer goods that can share information and complete tasks while you are busy with other activities.

Wireless Home Automation system(WHAS) using IoT is a system that uses computers or mobile devices to control basic home functions and features automatically through internet from anywhere around the world, an automated home is sometimes called a smart home. It is meant to save the electric power and human energy. The home automation system differs from other system by allowing the user to operate the system from anywhere around the world through internet connection.

This project presents a Home Automation System using Intel Galileo that employs the integration of cloud networking, wireless communication, to provide the user with remote control of various lights, fans and appliances within their home and storing the data in the cloud. The system will automatically change on the basis of sensors' data. This system is designed to below cost and expandable allowing a variety of devices to be controlled.

2.3 WIRELESS HOME AUTOMATION TECHNOLOGY USING INTERNET OF THINGS

IoT (Internet of Things) is fast emerging technology which involves interaction among things through internet without human interference. It has made human life easier and comfortable. This paper represents an affordable and flexible home control system using Arduino, web server with IP connectivity for interacting with devices and appliances remotely using Android based Smart phone app. It demonstrates the usefulness of the system using devices such as light switches, temperature sensors and water-level sensors. In addition to remote control it also provides reminders, voice command functionality. It is useful for people with physical disability.

Arduino is a popular open-source single-board microcontroller, which is designed to make the process of using electronics in multidisciplinary projects more accessible. The hardware consists of a simple open hardware design for the Arduino board with an Atmel AVR processor and on-board input/output support. The software consists of a standard programming language compiler and the boot loader that runs on the board. The Arduino board is a hardware interface allowing you to control and monitor hardware devices with your computer. We are

going to make a home automation system using the Arduino boards and the RS part components. There are many functions in our home automation system. These are some features about our system

2.4 IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNET OF THINGS FOR HOME AUTOMATION

Internet of Things (IoT) is a concept that envisions all objects around us as part of internet. IoT coverage is very wide and includes variety of objects like smart phones, tablets, digital cameras and sensors. Cloud based platforms help to connect to the things around us so that we can access anything at any time and any place in a user friendly manner using customized portals and in built applications. Hence, cloud acts as a front end to access IoT.

This paper presents an effective implementation for Internet of Things used for monitoring regular domestic conditions by means of low cost ubiquitous sensing system. It would effectively create a relay of machines that provide stimulus to each other and require the minimum human intervention. The description about the integrated network architecture and the interconnecting mechanisms for reliable measurement of parameters by smart sensors and transmission of data via internet is being presented. The framework of the monitoring system is based on combination of pervasive distributed sensing units, information system for data aggregation, reasoning.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Every user who is experienced in the existing system may think of a system that may add more flexibility. This work is designed in such a way to avoid the disadvantages of the existing system and supports more elasticity, comfort capacity and safety.

The main objective is to design and execute a cost effective and open source home automation system. The predictable system contains a great elasticity by using wireless reliable technology to interconnect various modules to the server. This in turn reduces the deployment cost; will add to the flexibility of advancement, and system reconfiguration. The projected system can make use of wireless LAN (Local space Network) connections between various sensors, hardware modules and server, and various communication protocols between users and server.

The proposed system is a distributed home automation system, consisting of server and sensors. Server controls and monitors the various sensors, and can be easily configured to handle more hardware interface module. The various sensors used here are PIR sensor, fire detecting sensor, gas leakage detecting sensor and relay drive. Relay drive is used to control and monitor the home appliances like lights, fans. PIR sensor is a motion detector that detects the presence of any intruders. Fire detecting sensor and gas leakage detecting sensor detects the presence of any fire accidents or gas leakage respectively. The home is regularly monitored and the data collected from these sensors are stored in the database. If any mishaps occur when the host is not at home, he/she gets an alert message along with image or video taken by the camera in his/her smart phone.

Fig 3.1 Architecture of Smart Home

3.1 IMPLEMENTATION MODULES

The modules are mainly divided into 3 sections as follows.

3.1.1 HOME

The home is regularly monitored using relay drive and various sensors like PIR sensor, fire detecting sensor and gas leakage sensor. Relay drive is used to control home appliances like light/fan. PIR sensor detects human presence and movement. Fire detecting sensor and gas leakage detecting sensor detects the presence of fire and gas leakage respectively. The data accumulated from these sensors are stored in the database and then analyzed. It helps to find whether any appliances are ON when not in use, whether any gas leakage or fire accident has occurred, whether an intruder has entered the house. If any problem is analyzed while processing the data, the client communicates with the server by sending requests. Here home is the client and server is in a virtual space.

3.1.2 SERVER

The server handles the requests received from the client. The requests are placed in a virtual space. After handling the requests, a teleport server is used from where we can get the result. We can obtain the data stored in the database through the teleport server.

For example: if the fire detecting sensor detects the presence of fire, it is this teleport server that sends the alert message and the images or video taken by the camera to the user's mobile phone & to the fire station.

3.1.3 APPLICATION

JSON is a lightweight data-interchange format. And by data-interchange format we mean a standard format that is used to transfer data from one language to another. It is a framework with which GUI is made. It is primarily used to transmit data between server and web applications.

IV. CONCLUSION

In Smart Home, we have introduced the event of a home management and security system exploitation using Raspberry pi and Internet of Things technology. The system is suitable for real-time home safety monitoring and for remotely controlling the home appliances and protection from fire accidents and gas leakage with immediate solutions. Any smart phone can be used to control different devices using web server. Such project can be very useful for old and physically disabled people.

The system may be employed in many places like banks, hospitals, labs etc that dramatically cut back the hazard of unauthorized entry. Proof may be given to the safety department if any theft issue happens. It also stores the sensor parameters in the cloud (Gmail) in a timely manner. This will help the user to analyze the condition of various parameters in the home anytime anywhere.

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